

THE ROLE OF A VALUABLE APPROACH IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY

Kalmuratov Imamatdin Tajitdinovich
Karakalpak state university, doctoral student
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Abstract. *This article shows the role of the value approach in the development of students' innovative activities and the importance of developing professional skills related to folk art.*

Keywords: *innovative activity, value, value approach, folk art, fine art.*

In the fifth direction of the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 called "Ensuring spiritual development and bringing the industry to a new level", "In-depth study and promotion of the rich scientific heritage of our great ancestors" was set as the priority aim (aim 73) [1]. As a result, in the process of studying the applied art of our ancestors, the possibility of further improvement of the mechanisms of development of innovative activity of students is expanding.

From time immemorial, mankind has passed the tried and tested pedagogical views on life from generation to generation. They are related to life, social and labor activities and events, and they gradually acquired a traditional character and served as a life lesson for the next generation and became a value.

The definition of "values - a complex of people, relationships, circumstances, material things and spiritual wealth that have prestige, attention, respect, influence among people in the society" is given in "Independence explanatory popular dictionary" [2].

The development of the concept of "value" makes it possible to distinguish different manifestations of values in a conditional way, to determine the driving forces of human nature, his desire to know, and cognitive activity. As a result of people's historical life lessons, thoughts and views about education are formed.

Of course, at the core of views on humanistic education in Central Asia are the traditions of folk art, applied art, as well as practical experiences, customs, ceremonies, national costumes, embroidery, painting. A. Allamuratov, a well-known Karakalpak art historian, has devoted his scientific research to the folk art of the Karakalpak people. The scientist's works "Karakalpak art from history" (1968), "Artistic features of Karakalpak folk embroidery" (1970), "My heritage" (1996), Karakalpak folk embroidery [3] are in demand today. has not lost its relevance due to its relevance. Also, in the scientist's scientific research, the decorative practical art of the Karakalpak people is aimed at showing the role of aesthetic, moral and ethical views of the decorative-practical art in the life of the people.

The practical art of the Karakalpak people differs from the art of other peoples with its unique pattern fragments in the state of semi-stylization and simplicity. In the sources related to his art, one can understand the past history of the people and thus notice the hardworking, simple-minded, generous hospitality of the people.

The art of painting in Karakalpak applied art has its own characteristics. For example, the artist determines the size of each pattern, which color it corresponds to, by beauty. Some patterns are small and very small, while some patterns need to be large and clearly visible. The beautiful appearance of the pattern depends on the person who made it, each pattern represented the life and

culture of the Karakalpak people. For example, in ancient times, it was possible to know how many children, how many grandchildren and even great-grandchildren she had from the patterns on the clothes of our elderly mothers. The worked patterns are accordingly branched like a river and often red threads are used in them.

When organizing events related to Karakalpak applied art, it is necessary to follow the following pedagogical and psychological principles:

1) Formation of future teachers' interest in working for the benefit of the general community; development of professional competences and professional skills related to folk art; development of the need and necessity to work; education of stable will qualities; to respond to the mentality and age characteristics of future teachers.

2) To explain to the students that in the developed countries of the world and in other countries, compared to the products made on modern machines in trade fairs and exhibition pavilions, practical art products made entirely by hand are appreciated;

3) To reproduce presentations, training manuals, methodical recommendations, articles and other information explaining Karakalpak applied art;

4) In the organization of classes related to applied arts, students should use new innovative, information and communication technologies (ICT) to organize lessons in practical classes in an interesting and meaningful way, not in the traditional way.

The role of the valuable approach in the development of students' innovative activities and the development of their professional competences related to folk art can be used in the following ways: in the study and presentation of new theoretical materials; organizing theoretical and practical training; in strengthening, controlling and checking the studied educational materials; in practical training of students; in open classes.

Valuable approaches to the development of innovative activities of students can be considered mainly the applied art of carpentry as the main tool. Studying Karakalpak applied art is carried out during practical classes, excursions, classroom and non-auditory classes, and during practical art events.

From time immemorial, the people of Karakalpak have used patterns to decorate their lives and make them beautiful in every way.

The pattern shows the national uniqueness of the people. We know well that the pattern is made mainly from nature scenes. Because nature presents beautiful landscapes to people. Humans acquire rich concepts based on natural phenomena. That is, it is considered to be a transition from a natural to an artistic one on the basis of stylization. The reason is that there are various colors, beauty, etc. in nature. is the basis for the origin of the actual pattern. While observing nature's manifestations, a person is interested in drawing like in fairy tales, giving its beauty as a pattern, he studies all the beauty of nature and uses it in his life. Then he expresses it through a pattern. Karakalpak art is also based on the expression of nature, and through the pattern, he showed his love for his native land and his interest in its nature. The Karakalpak people were able to create unique methods of coloring the patterns. One of the achievements of our people in the art of painting is to create patterns based not only on the nature, but also on the national traditions and living conditions of the people.

The people preserve their cultural heritage, which represents their lifestyle, in museums today. The museum named after I.V.Savitsky in the city of Nukus is considered to be a place where the great cultural heritage of our people is collected with local history materials. This heritage is

very necessary and valuable material for our youth today. It is useful for students to propose new ideas based on in-depth study of its exhibits as sources of their scientific research, to create a modern new design by applying fragments of pattern elements in practice. In educating the new generation of specialists, one of the urgent problems of the day is the ability to correctly interpret the values of the people of our multi-ethnic country, further develop their educational ideas and use them in new ways.

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